

ML objectives	User Experience Perspective				Infrastructure Perspective	
Problem & context Strong odors emitted by industrial units that make communities uncomfortable.	Accountability The operator is completely responsible for decisions taken in order to reduce community protests.	Cost The operator shall be aware of the sanctions in case of not preventing community protests.	Forcefulness Taking decisions based on the predictions is not mandatory.		Data streaming The data shall be streamed by the real-time data management system (Microsoft Stream Analytic tool).	
Organizational goals Avoid being sanctioned by the environmental authority for emitting strong odors.	Frequency The operator shall receive a prediction every 5 minutes.	Interactiveness The system shall grow data by receiving feedback from user interactions.	Value The operator shall have transparency on the reduction of complains.	Visualization The predictions of the model shall be presented in a dashboard in an interactive way according to the approved prototype.		Execution engine The model shall be deployed in a cloud computing service (Microsoft Azure).
User goals Odor emission alerts shall be accurate and allow decisions to be made to reduce community complains.	Data Perspective					Incremental Learning The data shall be continuously used to retrain the model when needed (data drift detection is required).
	Baseline The data shall meet the constraints (e.g., min max values, data types), defined in the baseline dataset.	Data operations ^E The data shall be normalized, dropped, resampled and encoded as needed.	Distribution ^E The dataset shall be split in some degree into training and test data.	Quantity ^E The training and test dataset shall have data points as needed to build a valuable model.	Source The data shall be searched in a database supported by the third-party data providing service.	
Model goals Accuracy, precision, recall shall be higher than 70%	Timeliness The data shall be available for use in real time.		Inherent data quality The data shall be real usage data and meet concerns related to ethics, accuracy, bias, completeness, consistency and credibility as much as possible.		Integration The dashboard shall consume the model as a web service (Microsoft Azure endpoint).	
ML functionality Classify the probability (high or low) of emitting strong odors that bother the community.	Model Perspective					Storage The ML artifacts (e.g., model, datasets, experiments) shall be stored in a cloud service on Microsoft Azure.
	Algorithm ^E Logistic regression.	Explainability The model shall provide information on the most importance features to explain its decisions.	Inference time The model shall infer its results in less than a minute.	Input & Output ^E Input: refinery variables and meteorological variables. Output: probability of having a community claim.	Learning time Training the model shall take one hour at most.	
Leading indicators Daily dashboard usage percentage and reduce the number of complaints from the community in 20%						
Customer expectations The system shall accurately classify the probability of emitting strong odors, allowing to prevent community complains.	Maintainability The model creation shall follow best coding practices (e.g., coding conventions PEP-8, SOLID design principals) and be documented according to docstring PEP-257.	ML problem type Predict categories (classification problem).	Model performance The model shall meet accuracy, precision and recall higher than 70%.	Model size The model size shall not break the inference time and the model explainability.	Reproducibility The creation/training of the model shall be automated by using a pipeline.	Telemetry The system shall collect and allow monitoring user interaction data and model performance.